

Wide-field Speckle Imaging from Both Hemispheres

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Although speckle imaging has been used in astronomy since the 1970s, it remains a somewhat mysterious method to many astronomers. At its essence, the reduction of speckle data is in the category of deconvolution problems in mathematics: the atmosphere acts as a linear, if complicated, operator on the image itself, and so this permits the deconvolution of the image if the point spread function (PSF) is sufficiently well known. Ideally, one would have an isolated point source very close to the object of interest and one could take speckle data simultaneously of both. However, the approximation of linearity only works over a small patch of sky, and usually there is not a bright point source close enough to the target of interest to satisfy this requirement.

The speckle technique is able to overcome the latter limitation so that, generally speaking, the PSF need not be measured at the same time as the object of interest. However, for a robust deconvolution, the point source data should be taken under the same atmospheric conditions (that is, similar statistics to the turbulent layer[s] creating the speckle effect, and therefore similar seeing). Nonetheless, a key advantage in working with speckle data is that the image improvements are obtained after the observation is complete, through mathematical manipulation of the images. This permits the reduction and analysis of the raw data in ways that can be changed later, tailoring to the image morphology itself. In a star cluster, for example, which may be viewed as a collection of point sources, a bright, reasonably isolated star in the cluster can serve as the PSF for the reconstruction. On the other hand, an extended object, like a planet or asteroid, may require a different reduction method to achieve the desired result.

The [‘Alopeke and Zorro](#) speckle cameras, built by Nic Scott, Steve Howell, one of us (E.H.), and Emmett Quigley, are permanently mounted on the telescopes at Gemini North and Gemini South, respectively. They have been designed to take advantage of this post-processing flexibility. In particular, a wide-field mode was designed into the optics that allows speckle data to be taken over a field of view of nearly 1 x 1 arcminute. While speckle methods have traditionally been used over fields of only a few arcseconds, we are currently developing analysis tools to extend the reach of the high resolution for which speckle is famous to the wide-field optical mode.

We show here two examples of promising results. In the first case, the globular cluster NGC 6723 was imaged with Zorro on Gemini South in July 2019. In Figure 1, we show both an integrated image and a wide-field speckle image reconstruction of a portion of the cluster near its center. The exposure time is about 18 minutes in total. The reduction methodology here was remarkably similar to that of normal speckle imaging. The central star, which was relatively bright, isolated, and unsaturated, was excised from the raw speckle data frames and a new data file of just that point source was created. This was then used as the point source in the standard speckle reduction for the original speckle frames using the method of bispectral analysis [1]. While this reconstruction was made over a field of view of approximately 37 arcseconds and not the full area of the wide-field mode, reconstructions of various sub-arrays over the full chip could be made with different point source candidates and a final image “stitched” together. Judging from the faintest stars seen in the reconstruction, we are

Figure 1. An integrated (left) and reconstructed (right) image of a region near the core of the globular cluster NGC 6723. Both images are on the same color scale, and the central star, used in the deconvolution, has been subtracted here so that fainter stars can more easily be seen. (Credit: International Gemini Observatory/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA)

approximately reaching the main sequence turn-off of the cluster at $V = 18$ to 19 mag; fainter magnitudes are probably achievable with longer exposure times. The resolution over the full field is improved from the seeing limit of 0.76 to 0.36 arcseconds in the reconstructed image, and there are a number of examples of stars that are severely blended in the original image but become clearly resolved in the reconstruction.

An example of a wide-field speckle reconstruction of an extended object is shown in Figure 2. These data of Jupiter were taken using the ‘Alopeke camera at Gemini North in December 2017, and first appeared in *Physics Today*. This is a very different situation from NGC 6723 from the point of view of image reconstruction. Here there is no point source on the field to use, so a bright point source was taken right after the speckle frames on the planet; the selected star was within a few degrees of Jupiter on the sky. The seeing

conditions throughout were relatively stable. Another change to the reduction method was to use the speckle frames only to derive the modulus of Jupiter’s Fourier transform. For the phase used in the reconstruction, which is a much lower signal-to-noise calculation when using the speckle data frames, the values derived from the integrated image were used to improve the signal-to-noise. Thus, for modulus and phase, different choices were made in the reduction to maximize the signal-to-noise and resolution of the final product. We hope to encode various options for the reduction of wide-field ‘Alopeke and Zorro data within the DRAGONS framework at Gemini in the future.

The gains in resolution seen in these reconstructions are not without cost, nor is wide-field speckle imaging a technique that can be expected to reach the diffraction limit. Improvement in resolution through image reconstruction is often achieved at the expense of limiting magnitude, and

Figure 2. Integrated (left) and reconstructed (right) images of Jupiter made in December 2017 with the ‘Alopeke camera at Gemini North. The diameter of Jupiter is about 43 arcsec. (Reproduced from [2], with the permission of the American Institute of Physics).

although wide-field speckle reductions are in their infancy, this is likely true here as well. More importantly, the wide-field mode for Zorro and ‘Alopeke has a pixel scale of 0.0725 arcseconds pixel^{-1} , and therefore speckles, which have a typical width of about 0.02 arcseconds at Gemini, are severely undersampled.

Nonetheless, what we find in the individual short-exposure wide-field speckle frames is that the stellar images retain a high-resolution “granular” appearance (presumably caused by pairs and triples of unresolved speckles) over a wider field than the traditional size of the isoplanatic angle. This makes sense—the information retrieved is not diffraction-limited, and therefore the correspondence between all speckles in one star’s speckle pattern need not be identical to those in another star in order to achieve improved resolution—that degree of linearity and PSF invariance is only needed for diffraction-limited resolution. Since the

wide-field methods focus on the retrieval of lower-resolution information (though still significantly higher than the seeing limit), the field-of-view requirement typically used in speckle imaging may be relaxed.

Both Zorro and ‘Alopeke are open to the community and available through regular Gemini queue, Fast Turnaround, and Director’s Discretionary Time proposals. We thank Steve Howell, Nic Scott, and Dan Nusdeo for conducting these observations.

References

- [1] [Lohmann, A. W., Weigelt, G., & Wirtitzer, B. 1983, *Applied Optics*, 22, 4028](#)
- [2] [Howell, S. B. & Horch, E. P. 2018, *Physics Today*, 71, 11, 78](#)